

Polarization Correction in Dual-Polarized Phased Arrays of Flared Notches

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Abstract—Though flared-notch radiators are capable of achieving very large bandwidths (10:1 or more) as radiating array elements, they are known to suffer from poor polarization purity when scanning in the diagonal plane (D-plane). This paper examines the polarization properties of dual-polarized arrays of flared notches as a function of frequency and the length/width ratio of the elements. Further, it is demonstrated through a combination of simulation and measurements that polarization degradation can largely be corrected for elements that have orthogonal feed ports. Though correctable, due to the nature of the polarization degradation that occurs in the D-plane, it is also shown that there is a limitation to the extent of correction that can be achieved.

Keywords—wideband phased arrays; flared notches; vivaldi; polarization degradation; cross polarization

I. INTRODUCTION

The flared notch is a popular radiator in phased arrays because it can achieve excellent matching ($1 < \text{VSWR} < 2$) over very large frequency bandwidths (10:1 or more). Flared-notch radiators exhibit excellent polarization characteristics in the principal planes (E-plane and H-plane), with easily better than 20dB of cross-polarization (x-pol.) rejection, but are known to have worse polarization purity in the diagonal plane (D-plane). While the cause of this degradation has been examined, both the degree and nature of this polarization degradation when scanning off axis have not been widely reported in the literature [1]. Given that flared notches continue to be routinely used as the front end for phased array systems, one could assume the level of polarization degradation is permissibly low, remaining within specifications. However, as will be shown in this study, the level of degradation can be quite severe, and could presumably have a major impact on system performance if not accounted for. As a general rule, by increasing the length of the flared notch radiator relative to the width, frequency bandwidth can be increased. However, it is also generally true that increasing the length of the flared notch has a negative impact on polarization characteristics. In general, the polarization degradation in the D-plane tends to be more severe in longer flared notches and similarly worse at higher frequencies, as shown in [2] [3]. The nature of this degradation and the relationship it has with frequency and the length/width (L/W) ratio of the radiator is examined in section II. In section III, this study will show that independent control

of the orthogonal feed ports in a typical dual-polarized array configuration can be used to systematically correct the polarization degradation to a certain extent. There are limitations to this correction depending on the geometry of the flared notch that need to be taken into account.

II. POLARIZATION DEGRADATION

This section explores the nature of the D-plane polarization degradation in flared notches. Consider excitation of the horizontal port only in the dual-polarized flared-notch pair. At broadside scan, the polarization purity is generally quite good, i.e. horizontal polarization (co-pol.) more than 20dB stronger than the vertical polarization (x-pol.). However, at higher scan angles in the D-plane, a point is reached where the polarization becomes circular – i.e., the vertical field component is just as strong as the horizontal field component, and 90 degrees out of phase. Scanning further, a point is reached where the vertical field component is significantly stronger than the horizontal field component. In other words, there is a scan angle in the D-plane where exciting the horizontal port produces a strongly vertical field.

The point at which these different grades of degradation occur are both a function of frequency and the ratio of the element length/width. For an ultra-wideband element, the effect is most pronounced at the high end of the frequency range. Similarly, the effect becomes more severe when the ratio of length/width of the element is too high. Short flared notches may never see the transition to circular polarization, as the angle may occur beyond the scan capacity of the array. This phenomenon is examined below.

A. Flared Notch Example

We begin by examining the polarization properties of the flared-notch element shown in Fig. 1. As shown in Fig. 2, the radiator achieves roughly 12:1 bandwidth at broadside scan with VSWR well below 2 for the full frequency range. The element has a length/width ratio of roughly 6.4, slightly more than three wavelengths long at the highest frequency of operation. As a consequence of the long flare length, the frequency bandwidth of the radiator is increased. Further details on the element can be found in [3].

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Figure 1. The profile of the flared notch examined in the first part of this study. The element has a L/W ratio of 6.4.

Figure 2. The broadside VSWR of the flared-notch radiator from Fig. 1.

Fig. 3(a) shows the measured E-plane element pattern for a central element of a small finite array. Results are typical for a radiator of this type – the co-pol. pattern rolls off smoothly with a $\cos(x)$ function ($1 < x < 2$), and the x-pol. is 20dB down. However, if one looks at a cut of the element pattern in the D-plane, as shown in Fig. 3(b), the element pattern shows x-pol. equal to the co-pol. at 29 degrees, and the x-pol. is significantly higher than the co-pol. near 45 degrees. This polarization reversal angle can easily fall within the scan volume for longer flared-notch radiators. Further, though it cannot be directly inferred from the plot, exciting just the horizontal port produces right-hand circular polarization at 29 degrees, with the polarization reversed when the vertical port is instead excited.

Figure 3. Measured element patterns of the notch in Fig. 1 at 8GHz; E-plane patterns show 20dB x-pol. rejection, but in the D-plane, x-pol. shows more complex behavior. Near 29 degrees, the polarization is circular, and near 45 degrees, the x-pol. is 20dB higher than the co-pol.

B. A. Degradation as a Function of Frequency

For the radiator in Fig. 1, Fig. 4 shows the D-plane scan angle at which point circular polarization is induced, and also the angle where polarization reversal (vertical field dominance with horizontal port excitation) occurs, as a function of frequency. These results are for a flared notch with an L/W ratio of 6.4:1, and the curves would be expected to shift down for elements with a larger L/W ratio, or up for elements with a smaller L/W ratio. As the plot shows, the CP angle falls well within the scan volume for most of the operational frequency range of the element.

C. Degradation as a Function of L/W Ratio

The primary factor controlling the degree of polarization degradation is the overall length of the radiator relative to the width. To underscore this relationship, a study of different length flared notches (similar to the one in Fig. 1) was conducted. Fig. 5 shows the relationship between the L/W ratio and scan angle polarization anomaly at the highest frequency of operation (given half-wavelength spacing). From this plot, it is apparent that longer notches have worse degradation, and that shorter radiators are less affected. These results are for an all-metal radiator of the type shown in Fig 1. However, tests were conducted on flared notches of various thicknesses, different types of construction and material properties ranging from all metal to substrate based, fin-type vs. body of revolution profiles, as well as various feed configurations. With some shifting, the nature of the polarization degradation is consistent across the various types of radiators tested. Hence, the curves of Fig. 5 can be used as a reasonable guide to polarization behavior vs. length in flared notches in general.

Figure 4. Characterizing the polarization degradation as a function of frequency for the notch in Fig. 1; Horizontal polarization first becomes right-hand circular, and then strongly vertical at higher scan. The degradation lessens at lower frequencies, pushing out to higher scan angles.

Figure 5. For a given L/W ratio, the D-plane scan angle at which point horizontal port excitation results in circular polarization and vertical polarization.

III. POLARIZATION CORRECTION

A. Correction Procedure

Typically, x-pol. rejection is an important performance metric in phased array systems. While the polarization degradation reported in the previous section may appear to reflect negatively on electrically-long flared notches, in dual-polarized configurations this behavior is largely correctable. Theoretically, in dual-polarized arrays with independent and orthogonal feed ports, it is possible to generate any desired polarization for any angle within the scan volume of the array. A procedure for correcting polarization degradation is given here. For a given scan angle, a transfer function is created from the uncorrected fields of the z-directed element as

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_{x,H}^0 & E_{x,V}^0 \\ E_{y,H}^0 & E_{y,V}^0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} a \\ b \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} E_x \\ E_y \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

First, the field components $E_{x,H}^0 / E_{y,H}^0$ are obtained from exciting just the horizontal feed port ($\{a \ b\}' = \{1 \ 0\}'$), repeating the procedure with just the vertical feed port active ($\{a \ b\}' = \{0 \ 1\}'$) to generate $E_{x,V}^0 / E_{y,V}^0$. This creates the transfer matrix, which is then inverted to determine the excitations required to generate the desired “goal” fields, or

$$\begin{bmatrix} E_{x,H}^0 & E_{y,V}^0 \\ E_{y,H}^0 & E_{y,V}^0 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \begin{Bmatrix} E_x^{goal} \\ E_y^{goal} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} a^{goal} \\ b^{goal} \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

B. Applying the Correction Procedure

The correction procedure was applied to the D-plane scan at 8GHz for an infinite array of the element shown in Fig. 1, attempting to generate strong horizontal polarization at all angles. The results of the correction are shown in Fig. 6. Uncorrected, the x-pol. ranges from -22dB at broadside to a positive 14.3dB as the polarization fluctuates from the desired horizontal polarization, changing to circular polarization and later vertical polarization in the scan plane. Using the correction procedure, strongly-horizontal polarization is achieved at all scan angles in the D-plane with better than 60dB of x-pol. rejection at all angles.

The results of Fig. 6 seem to indicate that the simple correction procedure can be used to correct polarization degradation, regardless of the severity. However, these results can be somewhat misleading, as the correction is merely local. In other words, by applying the correction procedure a deep null in x-pol. can be generated at the angle where the correction was applied, though elsewhere in the pattern x-pol. may still be undesirably high. To illustrate this, Fig. 7 shows the correction procedure applied to the element pattern of a central element of the 8x8 array previously introduced in [3]. The correction is applied at 29 degrees, and it is clear from Fig. 7 that there is roughly 35dB of x-pol. rejection at the desired angle. Compared to the uncorrected results in Fig. 3(b), the improvement is remarkable. However, it is also clear that

elsewhere in the element pattern, the x-pol. is still higher than the co-pol., e.g., at 60 degrees.

Figure 6. Applying the polarization correction procedure to the D-plane scan of the infinite element of Fig. 1. The correction procedure produces excellent correction for the entire scan plane.

Figure 7. Correction applied for a 29-degree scan in measured element. Compared to Fig. 3(b) which shows 0dB of x-pol. rejection, the correction creates 35dB of x-pol. rejection at the desired scan angle.

Figure 8. Measured D-plane pattern cut for 8x8 array scanned to 29 degrees at 8GHz, (a) uncorrected, (b) corrected; results shows almost 30dB of x-pol. rejection at the desired scan angle, though the correction has little effect on the rest of the pattern.

To demonstrate the effect of the correction procedure on measured finite array performance, Fig. 8(a) shows the uncorrected D-plane cut for an 8x8 array scanned to 29 degrees at 8GHz. The x-pol. rejection at 29 degrees is rather poor, where the polarization is circular instead of horizontal. After applying the correction procedure to the entire finite array, Fig. 8(b) shows that 30dB of x-pol. rejection can be achieved at the scan angle. The correction works well at 29 degrees, but elsewhere in the pattern cut the x-pol. is still high, i.e., there is potentially insufficient x-pol. rejection in the sidelobe regions. Similarly, Fig. 9(a) shows the uncorrected scan performance for the 8x8 array scanned to 50 degrees at 2GHz. Fig. 9(b) shows the corrected performance. The correction gives more than 25dB better x-pol. rejection. Compared to the higher frequency case, the correction works over a wider range of angles. The same would be expected if the correction procedure were applied to shorter radiators – i.e., for shorter radiators, the correction would have an effect over a wider range of angles.

Figure 9. Measured data from 8x8 array for a 50-degree scan at 2GHz, (a) uncorrected, (b) corrected; D-plane cut shows more than 30dB of x-pol. rejection at the desired scan angle with correction, effective over a much wider range compared to 8GHz case in Fig. 8.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an analysis of the polarization degradation that occurs when scanning flared-notch-type radiators in the D-plane. It is shown that for certain frequency ranges and certain radiator lengths, horizontal excitation can generate circular polarization and even vertical polarization. The degradation is studied as a function of frequency and also the length of the radiator, and shown to be worse for longer radiators and at higher frequencies. It is then shown that a correction procedure for dual-polarized radiators can be applied to correct for the degradation, regardless of frequency, radiator length, or severity of degradation. However, it is also shown that the correction effect is more localized for longer radiators and at higher frequencies, which is where the correction is most needed. Though this study was performed on flared notches, the findings would apply to many other types of radiators as well.

While there has been a push towards low-profile, high bandwidth radiators in recent years, this is normally attributed to factors such as cost, volume and weight, and simplicity of construction. This study shows clearly that profile has a significant impact on polarization in the D-plane as well. While it is true that flared notches can achieve large bandwidths as phased-array radiators, large bandwidth typically requires electrically-long elements. Because of the improved polarization properties of lower-profile radiators, this study would support the need for further research into low-profile radiators that can achieve ultra-wide frequency bandwidths.

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